

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF EFFICACY OF TACROLIMUS 0.03% OINTMENT VERSUS OLOPATADINE 0.2% EYE DROPS IN THE TREATMENT OF VERNAL KERATOCONJUNCTIVITIS (VKC)

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Abstract

Objective:

To compare the percentage change in the objective ocular sign score (OSS) between the Tacrolimus 0.03% ointment & Olopatadine 0.2% eye drops treatment groups in patients of Vernal Keratoconjunctivitis (VKC).

Methods:

This randomized controlled trial enrolled a total of 122 patients diagnosed with VKC. Patients in Group A received a 0.03% tacrolimus ointment, while those in Group B were administered 0.2% olopatadine eye drops. Both medications were applied twice daily throughout the study period. At week 24, the final examination was performed, and the final OSS value was calculated. These scores were used to compare A and B groups.

Results:

The mean age of included patients was 13.4±5.9 years. Regarding gender, there were 98 (80.3%) male patients and 24 (19.7%) female patients. Baseline OSS score was 9.1±2.1. After 20 weeks of treatment, the percentage reduction in OSS score was 97.2±1.0% in the tacrolimus group versus 81.5±3.5% in the olopatadine group (*p*-value <0.001).

Conclusion:

According to the results of present study, tacrolimus is superior to olopatadine for the treatment of VKC.

INTRODUCTION:

Vernal keratoconjunctivitis (VKC) is a long-term, bilateral inflammatory condition that affects the eyelids and ocular surfaces, often worsening seasonally—especially in spring—but it can persist year-round. It is characterized by an allergic

reaction involving the conjunctiva, which can involve the tarsal or bulbar regions, or both.¹ The condition usually manifests after the age of five and can last anywhere from two to ten years, often resolving after puberty.² VKC is more common among males and tends to occur in regions with

warm, dry, or subtropical climates, such as Japan, Pakistan, India, Thailand, various parts of South America, the Middle East, and Western countries.³

Vernal keratoconjunctivitis (VKC) presents in three primary forms: limbal, tarsal, and mixed. Patients often report symptoms such as a foreign-body sensation, ocular discomfort, blurred vision, intense itching, tearing, light sensitivity, and burning in the eyelids. Many also experience blepharospasm and mucous discharge upon waking.⁴ On examination, the conjunctiva typically shows redness, prominent papillae, discharge, and Horner-Trantas dots—gelatin-like limbal nodules associated with epithelial infiltrates. The cornea may also be involved, displaying a spectrum of lesions ranging from minor punctate epithelial erosions to more severe macroerosions and ulcers. These corneal changes can occur with or without neovascularization, particularly in cases involving the active palpebral form.⁵

Managing VKC necessitates a comprehensive approach that combines conservative strategies and pharmacological interventions.⁶ Patients are advised on fundamental eye care practices, such as avoiding eye rubbing, utilizing artificial tears, and applying cold compresses, alongside the elimination of known triggers. A thorough understanding of the disease's pathophysiology has led to the use of immunomodulators like Tacrolimus, in addition to traditional treatments including topical steroids, NSAIDs, vasoconstrictors, antihistamines, and mast cell stabilizers.⁷ While topical corticosteroids remain the most effective option for severe VKC cases, their use is associated with significant risks, including cataracts, glaucoma, and secondary infections, which can result in lasting visual impairment.⁸

It is essential to create new, more effective, and safer treatments to decrease the disease burden caused by vernal keratoconjunctivitis (VKC). At present, drugs like Olopatadine and Tacrolimus are used for prolonged symptom management in VKC patients.⁹ The aim of this study was to compare the percentage change in the objective ocular sign score (OSS) between the Tacrolimus

0.03% ointment & Olopatadine 0.2% eye drops treatment groups in patients of Vernal Keratoconjunctivitis (VKC).

METHODS:

This randomized controlled trial enrolled a total of 122 patients diagnosed with vernal keratoconjunctivitis (VKC). Participants were recruited from the outpatient department of the Institute of Ophthalmology at Mayo Hospital, Lahore, between October 2024 and March 2025. Eligible individuals ranged in age from 5 to 25 years and agreed to follow-up assessments. Patients were excluded if they had other ocular conditions such as glaucoma, uveitis, ocular infections, or corneal abnormalities; systemic illnesses, including hypertension or diabetes mellitus; or if they exhibited hypersensitivity to the medications involved in the study. Written informed consent was secured from each participant or their guardian.

Our ophthalmology team diagnosed VKC based on widely accepted criteria. The trainee gathered background information, conducted a general physical exam, and completed an eye examination. Initial objective sign scores (OSS) were recorded. A total of 122 patients were enrolled in the study, with 61 patients (50%) allocated to the tacrolimus group (A) and an equal number assigned to the olopatadine group (B). Prior to treatment, both topical and oral anti-allergic medications were halted for a period of two weeks. An initial assessment was conducted at baseline (0 weeks) to thoroughly document the presence and severity of VKC symptoms and signs. Patients in Group A received a 0.03% tacrolimus ointment, while those in Group B were administered 0.2% olopatadine eye drops. Both medications were applied twice daily throughout the study period.

Patients were reviewed at weeks 2, 4, 8, 12, 16, and 20, and OSS was calculated. At week 24, the final examination was performed, and the final OSS value was calculated. These scores were used to compare A and B groups.

Data was analyzed using SPSS v25. Mean OSS score between the groups was compared using an independent sample t-test, taking p-value ≤ 0.05 as significant association.

RESULTS:

The mean age of included patients was 13.4±5.9 years. Regarding gender, there were 98 (80.3%) male patients and 24 (19.7%) female patients. Baseline OSS score was 9.1±2.1 (Table 1).

After 24 weeks of treatment, the percentage reduction in OSS score was 97.2±1.0% in the

tacrolimus group versus 81.5±3.5% in the olopatadine group (p-value <0.001). There was a considerable reduction in OSS symptoms in both groups, but the reduction was greater in the tacrolimus group (Table 2).

Table 1. Baseline Study Characteristics (N=122).

Variable	Value
Age (Years)	13.4±5.9
<i>Gender (%)</i>	
Male	98 (80.3%)
Female	24 (19.7%)
Baseline OSS Score	9.1±2.1

Table 2. Comparison of OSS Score at 24 weeks Follow-up.

	Tacrolimus group (N=61)	Olopatadine group (N=61)	p-value
At 24 Weeks	97.2±1.0%	81.5±3.5%	<0.001

DISCUSSION:

The management of Vernal Keratoconjunctivitis (VKC) generally includes preventive measures, medical treatments, and surgical interventions. Preventive strategies involve vaccination and the avoidance of allergens such as house dust mites, pollen, and dust. Surgical procedures are typically considered for severe cases and may involve excising large conjunctival papillae or debriding persistent shield ulcers. For acute VKC, medical therapy is the primary approach, utilizing topical antihistamines, mast cell stabilizers, mucolytics, and lubricants as initial treatments. In more severe or persistent cases, corticosteroid eye drops and supratarsal steroid injections are often added to better manage symptoms.¹⁰ However, prolonged or inappropriate use of topical steroids can lead to serious side effects, including glaucoma, cataracts, and secondary infections. Children with VKC are especially vulnerable to steroid-related complications because they are the most commonly affected age group.¹¹

Second-generation antiallergic medications are now the preferred choice for managing vernal keratoconjunctivitis (VKC), due to their dual action as antihistamines and mast cell stabilizers. Olopatadine is a notable example; it selectively

blocks the H1 histamine receptor, preventing histamine release and ensuring mast cells remain stable. It has become the most widely used treatment for allergic conjunctivitis, often in combination with topical steroids. The U.S. Food and Drug Administration has approved olopatadine in strengths of 0.1%, 0.2%, and 0.7% specifically for allergic conjunctivitis.^{12,13}

The U.S. Food and Drug Administration approved the use of this medication at concentrations of 0.1%, 0.2%, and 0.7% for the treatment of allergic conjunctivitis. Tacrolimus, an immunosuppressive agent derived from *Streptomyces tsukubaensis*, exhibits a potency that surpasses cyclosporine by a factor of 100.¹⁴ It is classified as a nonsteroidal macrolide, although its exact mechanism of action remains partially understood. It is believed to inhibit the activation of Th2 lymphocytes—key cells involved in VKC—as well as the proliferation of B cells facilitated by T helper cells and the production of cytokines.¹⁵ Originally used primarily to prevent organ rejection in liver transplants, tacrolimus has expanded its applications to other types of organ transplants and is now employed in treating various skin conditions such as vitiligo and atopic

dermatitis. Different formulations and dosages of tacrolimus have been studied, but findings regarding its safety and effectiveness are inconsistent. In a specific trial, both 0.03% tacrolimus and 0.2% olopatadine demonstrated significant reductions in VKC symptoms, leading to strong recommendations for their use. After three months of treatment, patients receiving tacrolimus exhibited fewer persistent signs and symptoms compared to those treated with olopatadine, with this difference reaching statistical significance.^{16, 17}

This study found that patients treated with either 0.03% tacrolimus or 0.2% olopatadine experienced substantial improvements, with a notable reduction in the severity of their symptoms. Both medications proved to be effective options for managing VKC. However, a statistically significant difference was observed between the two drugs, indicating that patients in the tacrolimus group exhibited fewer signs and symptoms after three months of treatment compared to those in the olopatadine group.

Similar to the findings of this study, Sameera Irfan and colleagues demonstrated that applying 0.03% tacrolimus ointment topically is both safe and effective for managing moderate to severe VKC. However, unlike our study, their results showed a different trend in the overall percentage of improvement observed in signs and symptoms.¹⁸

In a different double-masked, randomized comparative study, Lab-charoenwongs et al. found that 0.1% tacrolimus eye ointment was effective in treating children with active vernal keratoconjunctivitis (VKC) after four weeks of therapy. The group receiving tacrolimus experienced an overall symptom improvement of 86.49% from baseline, a result that was statistically significant.²

In a separate investigation, Vichyanond and colleagues employed tacrolimus as a long-term treatment for severe VKC, observing no notable adverse effects. Extended application of tacrolimus resulted in a decrease in both clinical symptoms and papillary formations.¹⁹

Muller and colleagues conducted a comparative analysis involving 21 patients suffering from severe VKC. Their research indicated that adding

olopatadine to a 0.03% tacrolimus treatment did not produce additional benefits. Both groups showed reductions in symptom scores—by 1.7 ± 3.9 in the group receiving tacrolimus with olopatadine and by 0.6 ± 1.6 in the group receiving tacrolimus with a placebo—with no statistically significant difference observed between the two cohorts.²⁰

While this research has certain limitations, such as a limited diversity in the sample population and a relatively brief follow-up period, its significance stems from integrating both subjective impressions and objective metrics in analyzing a large sample size. Nevertheless, further research with extended follow-up durations is necessary to establish the long-term safety and effectiveness of this medication.

CONCLUSION:

According to the results of present study, tacrolimus is superior to olopatadine for the treatment of VKC.

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